

DAMAGE ANALYSIS OF ALUMINUM / CFRP HYBRID BEAM UNDER THREE POINT BENDING

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Keywords: *Progressive Damage Mechanics, FEA, Hybrid beam, CFRP, Square hollow section*

1 Introduction

Aluminum hollow section beam has been widely used as structural member. However, the strength of aluminium alone is insufficient to be used for some special applications such as extremely light weight vehicle, aerospace vehicle, and so on. Reinforcing the aluminum by fiber reinforced plastic has been studied to increase the strength without excessive increasing of total mass. Moreover, the catastrophic failure which is a critical drawback of composite could be guided by the plastic deformation of the aluminum, allowing the failure mode to be changed to progressive failure mode [1]. As a result, specific energy absorption (SEA), which is the absorbed energy per mass, can also be enhanced simultaneously

In general, under a small bending load, a metal-composite hybrid SHS beam shows linear elastic behavior, and subsequently shows plastic buckling behavior with further loading. Finally, the beam will show bending collapse behavior when the load exceeds a critical value. The bending collapse behavior can be analyzed by a Kecman's model and modified Kecman's model [1]. However, it is difficult to describe the intermediate status when plastic buckling of metal and local damage of composite material begin to occur with an analytic model. The failure modes of composites are very complex and are not readily described by simple theoretical models. Delamination between laminates and debonding between aluminum and composites complicate this further. Nowadays, the failure model of composites and delamination analysis have been advanced with the increasing of computational power.

For FEA, a progressive damage evolution model has been studied to analyze the failure of composites materials [2, 3]. To predict damage initiation, various criteria have been proposed, such as stress,

strain, Tasi-Wu, Hashin, Puck, LaRC, and so on[4,5]. To simulate damage evolution, material property (stiffness) degradation methods based on continuum damage mechanics have shown valuable results. Recently, energy based damage evolution was implemented in commercial software, ABAQUS[6, 7]. The energy based damage evolution law is defined in terms of the fracture energy dissipated during the damage process. This evolution law is a generalization of the cohesive zone model (CZM) for modeling delamination using cohesive elements [8].

Analysis of delamination has been an important area of research since the development of laminated composites. The virtual crack closure technique (VCCT) is a well-known approach to simulate interface crack problems [9]. However, it is only applicable to 2D and self-similar crack propagation. For more complex geometry and application, the cohesive zone model proposed by Dugdale and Barenblatt [10] has been extensively developed for application to delamination [11, 12]. It is assumed that there is a process zone in front of the crack tip. Damage initiates when the status of stress or strain meets certain criteria. The process zone is controlled by traction separation laws.

In this study, failure mechanism of aluminum-composite hybrid beam under the three point bending was investigated by finite element analysis (FEA). The shape of aluminum was square hollow sectioned and applied composite was carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP).

2 Discretization of Aluminum-CFRP Hybrid Beam

Fig. 1 is a schematic of the aluminum-CFRP hybrid beam. A square hollow section (SHS) aluminum beam was wrapped by four plies of CFRP

laminates with designed stacking sequence. The thickness of a ply was 0.146mm and total thickness of 4 plies of CFRP in the hybrid beam was 0.584mm [13]. Five kinds of lay-up sequence are considered: $[0^\circ]_4$, $[90^\circ]_4$, $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_2$, $[45^\circ/-45^\circ]_2$, and $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]$.

Fig. 1. Schematic of aluminum-CFRP square hollow section beam

Fig. 2. FEA model of aluminum-CFRP hybrid beam

The bending behavior was analyzed by explicit finite element analysis (ABAQUS/Explicit). Fig. 2 is a FEA model of the SHS beam. The aluminum beam is modeled as two layers of 3D hexahedral continuum linear solid incompatible elements with eight nodes. The layer of CFRP is divided into two regions considering accuracy of analysis and computational cost. The region where large deformation may occur is modeled as multiple layers of continuum shell elements that have a homogeneous laminar property at each layer with 3 integration points through the thickness direction. Damage of CFRP and delamination are considered

at every ply, and the size effect of damage evolution is alleviated by refining the size of the mesh. Element size is 0.4 mm x 0.4 mm. The remaining region far from the loading nose is modeled as one layer of a continuum shell that has a composite section property. Continuity between the multilayered continuum shell and single layered continuum shell elements is achieved by multi-point constraints. Interlaminar damage and interface debonding are modeled by a cohesive element. For cohesive layers, three dimensional 8 node cohesive elements (COH3D8) elements have been used. The thickness of a cohesive element is assumed to be 5 μm. The loading nose and supporting rods are modeled as a rigid surface. Interaction between the supporting rod and specimen is assumed to have surface to surface contact with a friction coefficient $\mu=1.0$ and finite sliding is allowed. Regarding the asymmetry induced by 45° or -45° direction ply, full dimensions are modeled. Interaction between the loading nose and the specimen is assumed to have general contact with a friction coefficient $\mu=1.0$. In addition to the exterior surface, interior surfaces defined by inside elements are also reserved as a potential contact pair. At the initial stage, only the exterior surface of the CFRP contacts with the loading nose. Once an element is fully damaged and removed, new surfaces exposed by the removed element are activated. The new surfaces are allowed to contact with each other.

Appropriate displacement boundary conditions are assigned at two nodes of the lower wall to prohibit rigid body motion. The loading nose moves quasi-statically 5mm downward in a minute.

Fig. 3 Deformed shape of hybrid beam $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]$ under 5mm of nose distance (contour represents the magnitude of deformation)

Fig. 3 is a typical deformed shape of the hybrid beam. Nonlinear elasto-plasticity was considered for aluminum and progressive damage mechanics was applied for the CFRP. Hashin damage initiation criteria and energy based damage evolution were applied [14]. Delamination and debonding were modeled by cohesive zone model under traction separation law and energy based damage evolution [15, 16]. For numerical analysis, material properties of aluminum, failure characteristics of CFRP laminate, and adhesion between aluminum and CFRP were measured experimentally.

3 Modeling and Calibration

3.1 Progressive Damage Modeling of CFRP

A CFRP laminate may initiate to fail when one of following indexes is greater than or equal to one, which is the Hashin Criteria. Four failure modes; fiber tension, fiber compression, matrix tension, and matrix compression, are considered and are represented separately as follows [4]

Fiber tension

$$F_f^t = \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{11}}{X^T} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\hat{\tau}_{12}}{S^L} \right)^2 \quad (1)$$

Fiber compression

$$F_f^c = \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{11}}{X^C} \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

Matrix tension

$$F_m^t = \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{22}}{Y^T} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\hat{\tau}_{12}}{S^L} \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

Matrix compression

$$F_m^c = \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{22}}{2S^T} \right)^2 + \left[\left(\frac{Y^C}{2S^T} \right)^2 - 1 \right] \frac{\hat{\sigma}_{22}}{Y^C} + \left(\frac{\hat{\tau}_{12}}{S^L} \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

where σ_{ij} are components of the effective stress tensor, X^T and X^C are the tensile and compressive strengths in the fiber direction, and Y^T and Y^C are the tensile and compressive strengths in the matrix direction. S^L and S^T denote the longitudinal and transverse shear strengths.

The constitutive equation of the material is

$$\sigma = C_d \varepsilon \quad (5)$$

where σ is stress and ε is strain. The stiffness matrix C_d reflects damage and has the form

$$C_d = \frac{1}{D} \begin{bmatrix} (1-d_f)E_1 & (1-d_f)(1-d_m)\nu_{21}E_1 & 0 \\ (1-d_f)(1-d_m)\nu_{12}E_2 & (1-d_m)E_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & D(1-d_s)G_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where d_f , d_m , and d_s are damage variables for tension, compression, and shear, respectively. Damage variable $D = 1 - (1 - d_f)(1 - d_m)\nu_{12}\nu_{21}$. E_1 , E_2 , and G_{12} are material properties of undamaged status, and ν_{12} and ν_{21} are the corresponding Poisson's ratios [8, 17].

Once the damage initiation criterion in (1) ~ (4) is satisfied, further loading will cause degradation of the material stiffness coefficients as a function of the damage variable d_i , ranging from zero (undamaged) to one (fully damaged).

The in-built damage evolution law for the damage variable in ABAQUS is used to simulate the in-ply damage in each lamina. The damage evolution law is defined in terms of the fracture energy dissipated during the damage process, which is a generalization of the cohesive zone model (CZM) for modeling delamination using cohesive elements.

3.2 Cohesive Zone Model

Delamination between laminas with different fiber orientation and debonding between aluminum and CFRP were modeled by the cohesive zone model with the traction separation law. As described in section 2, the interface between the aluminum and the CFRP and the interlayers between laminas are discretized by cohesive elements. The applied conditions for this analysis are briefly summarized in this section.

Fig. 4. Coordinates of traction vectors

Damage was assumed to initiate when a quadratic interaction of a function involving the nominal stress ratios reaches a value of one. This criterion can be represented as [17]

$$\left\{ \frac{\langle t_n \rangle}{t_n^o} \right\}^2 + \left\{ \frac{t_s}{t_s^o} \right\}^2 + \left\{ \frac{t_t}{t_t^o} \right\}^2 = 1 \quad (7)$$

where t is a nominal traction stress vector. The subscripts n , s , and t represent the normal, first shear, and second shear direction, respectively, as shown in Fig. 4. The superscript 0 represents the peak value of nominal stress. The symbol $\langle \rangle$ is a Macaulay bracket and denotes the positive part.

The stress components of the traction-separation are affected by the damage according to

$$\begin{aligned} t_n &= (1-d)\langle \bar{t}_n \rangle \\ t_s &= (1-d)\bar{t}_s \\ t_t &= (1-d)\bar{t}_t \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where d is a damage variable and the over bar on t represents the stress components predicted by the elastic traction-separation behavior for the current strains without damage. Damage evolution is defined based on energy that is dissipated as a result of the damage process. A criterion proposed by Benzeggagh-Kenane was used:

$$G_n^c + (G_s^c - G_n^c) \left(\frac{G_s + G_t}{G_n + G_s + G_t} \right)^\eta = G^c \quad (9)$$

where G is the fracture energy, the superscript c represents the critical fracture energy, and η is a material parameter [18].

4 Results of FEA

The behavior of the hybrid beam was analyzed by the model shown in Fig. 2. For reasonable computational time, mass scale of 1000 was applied [26], where kinetic energy was less than 0.1% of total strain energy. Stable time increment was 9.054×10^{-7} second. The computation time was about 25

hours on a workstation with Intel Core i7 (Hexa Core).

Fig. 3 shows a typical deformed shape of the Al / CFRP $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]$ specimen by bending force of the loading nose at 2.5 mm displacement. In the following, for convenience, the hybrid specimen is identified by indicating the stacking sequence. It is shown that the upper and lower walls are bent down by bending moment, and the front and back walls protrude due to plastic buckling of the aluminum. The region contacting with the loading nose shows large deformation. The upper wall directly contacting with the loading nose is compressed by the loading nose, and excessive deformation occurs, surrounding the cylindrical shape of the loading nose.

Fig. 5. Von Mises stress field at each ply of $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]$ specimen at nose displacement of 2.5mm (a) 1st ply 0° , (b) 2nd ply 45° , (c) 3rd ply 90° , and (d) 4th ply -45° .

Fig. 5 (a) - (d) shows von-Mises stress fields of each CFRP layer of the $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]$ stacking sequence specimen at 2.5 mm displacement. It is clearly shown that the stress field strongly depends on the direction of the carbon fibers and the stacking sequence of the laminate. Elastic modulus along the fiber direction is much higher than that along the transverse direction, and stress along the fiber direction is also high. Note that the damage criteria are applied for each layer and interface.

From the FEA, it was observed that the fracture of the CFRP laminate and delamination between layers are strongly interconnected. Delamination separated the stacked laminates and resulted in decreased CFRP strength. Separated laminate was weakened and fractured easily. The broken CFRP was

compressed between the aluminum and the downward loading nose, broken off, or split into several small sections. The center of the upper edge contacting with the loading nose was the stress concentration region. Damage began at the edge, and expanded to the radial direction in the side walls (both front and back) and propagated into the inner layers of the CFRP. When the loading nose reached approximately 0.584 mm, which was close to the thickness of the CFRP, plastic buckling of aluminum and debonding between the CFRP and the aluminum occurred.

Fig. 6. Equivalent plastic strain at aluminum (a) only aluminum, and (b) hybrid beam

A typical characteristic of the interior aluminum is shown in Fig. 6 in terms of equivalent plastic strain. For better understanding, only the left edge part of the beam is shown. The observed time step is at 2.5 mm displacement, which corresponds with when the aluminum specimen showed peak load. The stacking sequence of the hybrid specimen is $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]$. As shown in the figure, equivalent plastic strain (PEEQ) is concentrated at the edge under the loading nose. Compared with the aluminum specimen, the hybrid specimen shows a low strain value and a small area of influence. This means that the CFRP laminate supported the interior aluminum and resulted in small plastic deformation at the weak region.

Damage accumulation and evolution in the interlayers are shown in Figs. 7 and 8. There are three interlayers in this specimen. In the figure, fully

damaged elements are removed as the load increases and resembles a semicircular shaped hole in the specimen. At nose displacement of 0.47mm, the first interlayer (between the first ply and the second ply) remains. However, the third interlayer (between the third ply and the fourth ply) begins to fail, as shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Damage accumulation in each interlayer at loading nose displacement of 0.47 mm. (a) Legend and location, (b) 1st interlayer, (c) 2nd interlayer, and (d) 3rd interlayer.

Fig. 8. Damage accumulation of each interlayer at loading nose displacement of 2.5 mm. (a) Legend and location, (b) 1st interlayer, (c) 2nd interlayer, and (d) 3rd interlayer.

At nose displacement of 2.5mm, the area of damage becomes wider, as shown in Fig. 8. It is interesting that the damaged area at the first interlayer is the widest, unlike Fig. 7, followed by the second and the third interlayers. As will be shown in Fig. 9, at this time, a wide region at the interface is already debonded, and the CFRP and aluminum are separated. As a result, the first interlayer close to the debonded interface is damaged easily.

Fig. 9. Debonding of interface as a function of nose displacement. (a) 0.47 mm, (b) 1.1 mm, (c) 1.94 mm, and (d) 2.5 mm.

Fig. 9 shows sequential damage status at the interface between the aluminum and the CFRP. Similar to the previous interlayer, the damaged area (removed element) increases with loading displacement, but the debonding area is much larger than the delaminated region. The shape of delamination varies depending on the stacking sequence, but generally shows a peanut shape.

Fig. 10. Photos of damage at the edge after loading displacements of (a) 0.6 mm, (b) 1.55 mm, and (c) 3.0mm

Damage at the edge was verified experimentally. Fig. 10 shows edge damage of the $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]$ specimen for three loading nose displacements: 0.6 mm, 1.55 mm, and 3.0 mm. Load was applied up to the desired displacement and then reloaded. The

damaged edge was captured by a low scope camera. At 0.6 mm displacement, permanent deformation is shown. Considering the behavior of aluminum in Fig. 11, at this displacement, aluminum deforms in an elastic range and recovers its original shape when the loading nose is unloaded. Thus, permanent deformation is induced by irreversible damage of the CFRP, as shown in Fig. 7. At 1.55 mm displacement, in Fig. 10(b), the color of the CFRP under the loading nose is changed from black to white, which is induced by plastic deformation of the resin in the CFRP laminate, and the interior aluminum begins to be revealed. At 3.0 mm displacement, in Fig. 10(c), the region of white colored CFRP becomes large. Aluminum is clearly shown, resulting from the removal of the extremely damaged CFRP. Considering the delamination behavior in Fig. 14, it is evident that the delaminated CFRP layer separated from the aluminum, and fractured sequentially with increasing force of the loading nose.

Fig. 11. FEA results of load displacement curve

Load-displacement curves of five hybrid beams are plotted in Fig. 11. Explicit analysis under the displacement boundary condition makes reaction force noisy. Therefore, a Savitzky-Golay smoothing with a second-order polynomial and 50 points of window was applied to filter the data. The peak load of stacking sequence $[90^\circ]_4$ is about 11.6 kN and is the lowest among the considered specimens. The load shows a gradual slope around the peak load. Stacking sequence $[0^\circ]_4$ shows a similar trend to stacking sequence $[90^\circ]_4$. In the case of stacking

sequence $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_2$, critical displacement to the peak is delayed by about 0.5 mm, and the corresponding peak load is slightly higher than those of $[0^\circ]_4$ and $[90^\circ]_4$. Stacking sequences $[45^\circ/-45^\circ]_2$ and $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]$ show marked increases of peak load and delay of the critical displacement. Stacking sequence $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]$ shows the maximum peak load. It can be inferred that the reinforcing effect of the CFRP is pronounced in stacking sequence $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]$. It is shown that the performance of the hybrid SHS beam is strongly dependent on the behavior of the load curve at about 3.0 mm displacement, whether the load is further increased or unchanged. When the reinforcing effect is retained, such as in the cases of $[45^\circ/-45^\circ]_2$ or $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]$, the load continues to increase.

Fig. 12. Representative load-displacement behavior of Al / CFRP SHS beam specimen depending on lay-up sequences, redrawn from the experimental results

For comparison, experimental results in reference [13] are redrawn up to a nose displacement of 5mm in Fig. 12. A detailed explanation about the experimental results can be found in reference [13]. Overall behavior of the numerical results in Fig. 11 are very close to the experimental results in Fig. 12. As expected by the FEA, $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]$ shows the maximum peak load, followed by $[45^\circ/-45^\circ]_2$ and $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_2$. The peak loads of $[0^\circ]_4$ and $[90^\circ]_4$ are very close, but $[90^\circ]_4$ is slightly higher than $[0^\circ]_4$. However, in the FEA, $[0^\circ]_4$ is slightly higher than $[90^\circ]_4$. This resulted from an abrupt load drop at about 2.7mm displacement. The FEA model in this

study showed a limitation such as an abrupt drop, and a detailed illustration

Fig. 13. Normalized bending stiffness of the Al / CFRP hybrid SHS beam based on Al / CFRP $[0^\circ]_4$ case

In Fig. 11, the loads of all cases showed a similar trend before about 1.5 mm displacement. At this small load, the damaged area was small and deformation was strongly dependent on the elastic properties of the hybrid SHS beam. Therefore, for comparison, bending stiffness (load / displacement) of the hybrid beams is calculated at 0.25 mm displacement. For this stiffness calculation, the same mesh as the damage model is used, but only linear elastic properties are applied. Calculated stiffness is shown in Fig. 13. The variation of stiffness is about 12.5 %. The bending stiffness of the $[90^\circ]_4$ case is slightly lower than that of the $[0^\circ]_4$ case, but both the $[90^\circ]_4$ and $[0^\circ]_4$ cases are much lower than the $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]$, $[45^\circ/-45^\circ]_2$, and $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_2$ cases. It appears that the stiffness calculated from the linear elastic analysis offers reasonable results. However, it is interesting that the bending stiffness of $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]$ is much lower than that of $[45^\circ/-45^\circ]_2$. However, as shown in Fig. 16, a full analysis showed the highest load at $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]$. Therefore, it is shown that a simple stiffness calculation is not sufficient to describe the response of the hybrid SHS beam under large bending deformation.

5 Summary

Finite element analysis showed that stresses were concentrated at the edges under the loading nose and resultant damage and failure were observed. At first, damage of CFRP and delamination were occurred. Then debonding between aluminum and CFRP was occurred and followed by plastic buckling of aluminum and bending collapse behavior of the hybrid beam. Overall performances of the hybrid beam represented by load-displacement curves with respect to the stacking sequence of laminate were compared with experimental results. FEA results showed good agreement with the experimental results. And it was observed that the direction of laminates made great effect on the performance of hybrid beam.

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